

Speculation on Spin and the Pauli Exclusion Principle

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The Pauli exclusion principle applies to bosons and fermions. The latter have symmetric wavefunctions (on the interchange of two identical particles for example) and the latter, antisymmetric. This means that if two fermions have the same momentum and are at the same position and one wishes this factor of the wavefunction to be symmetric, one must have the spin factor of the wavefunction be antisymmetric. Thus, one cannot have both fermions with spin up (or both with spin down) and have both fermions at the same spatial position. As a result, spin is very important for the Pauli exclusion principle. In fact, particles with rest mass m_0 usually have spin $\frac{1}{2}$, while bosons, like light (spin 1) have an integer spin.

In a previous note, we argued that spin arises by writing an equation that is linear in the intrinsic force of a particle (because force appears linearly in nature e.g. $F = dp/dt$), but is linked at the same time to E, p (energy, momentum) and geometry. In the case of a particle with rest mass, we argued that rest mass m_0 is the intrinsic force because it is inertia, while for a photon, it is the electric field (together with the magnetic) which is the intrinsic force.

Thus, $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ (free particle wavefunction with no spin) applies to both a photon and a particle with rest mass (e.g. electron), but the spins are very different as are the Pauli exclusion principle rules. To find the electron spin, one must linearize $-EE + p \cdot p = -m_0 m_0$ ($c=1$) (following Dirac's approach), while for a photon one may linearize $d/dt \text{ partial} (.5\epsilon_0 E \cdot E + .5/\mu_0 B \cdot B) + \text{grad partial dot} (E \times B) = 0$ or obtain a linear equation directly from Maxwell's equations. In one case, one finds 4×4 matrices linked to Pauli's 2×2 matrices (2 choices) for spin $\frac{1}{2}$, while in the other case, the matrix is ϵ_{ijk} (the Levi-Civita symbol) (i for the matrix label, j, k for entries) which applies to spin 1. We ask in this note: How is the Pauli exclusion principle linked to the intrinsic force?

For a particle with rest mass, we suggest that the key idea is that there should exist an interaction which may separate the center-of-masses of two identical particles. One way to do so is via an impulse hit on momentum, but another is to have a magnetic field acting on spin projections. If two identical particles with rest mass and the same momentum are at the same spatial point, there must be a way, via a physical interaction, to separate the center-of-masses, and this requires opposite spin projection directions (so two beams are created as in the original experiments). We note that given $-EE + pp = -m_0 m_0$, changing m_0 to $2m_0$ still satisfies this equation and spin remains $\frac{1}{2}$, so one must have a way of distinguishing the particle centers-of-mass through an interaction which is how one defines two particles with rest mass.

In the case of a photon, there is no rest mass and no need to distinguish the centers-of-mass via an interaction, but one must still distinguish between the two particles. We suggest that once again one should consider the intrinsic force, in this case the electric field. Two identical photons may have the same E (in the same direction) which adds to $2E$ (and $2B$), but energy is linked to $2(.5\epsilon_0 E \cdot E + .5/\mu_0 B \cdot B)$ and so even though $2E$ and $2B$ add and one would feel an electric force proportional to $2E$, the energy and momentum densities would not correspond to a single photon with an electric field of $2E$ and magnetic $2B$. For a particle with rest mass, two identical particles with m_0 and v , have $E+E = 2m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ and $p+p = 2m_0 v / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$

(one dimension), but these are exactly the same results for a single particle with mass $2m_0$ and v . One needs to distinguish the two particles through two separate center-of-masses, we argue.

The Pauli Exclusion Principle

The Pauli exclusion principle (2) states that two identical fermions (half-integer spins) cannot occupy the same quantum numbers, while integer spin bosons may. As stated in (1), this exclusion principle is directly linked to the quantum notion of spin. In (1), we argued that an equation for spin arises by identifying the intrinsic force of a particle. For a particle with rest mass, the intrinsic force is m_0 , i.e. inertia, while for a photon it is E/c , the electric field (which is linked to a B magnetic field). As a result, both a photon (no rest mass, spin 1) and electron (spin $\frac{1}{2}$ fermion with rest mass) have the same free particle wavefunction (ignoring spin)

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((1))$$

because both have an energy E and momentum p associated with special relativity and no rest mass appears directly in ((1)). As a result, both may produce two-slit interference patterns if slits are about \hbar/p apart. Why is it then that the spins of an electron and photon are so different and that each behaves very differently according to Pauli's exclusion principle?

We suggest that the reason lies in analysis of the driver of spin, which we have argued in (1) is the intrinsic force of a particle.

Intrinsic Force of a Particle and Its Relation to Identical Particles

We stated above that a particle with rest mass m_0 has an intrinsic force of m_0 , inertia, while a photon's intrinsic force is E/c , the electric field. Both are physical measurables and should appear in a linear equation (like $dp/dt=F$ etc) because forces appear linearly in nature. In the case of a rest mass m_0 , special relativity gives the equation:

$$-EE + p \cdot p = -m_0 m_0 \quad (c=1) \quad ((2))$$

This is quadratic in the intrinsic force and so should be linearized as Dirac has shown. This leads to 4x4 matrices (as one cannot linearize this equation simply with numbers), and the 4x4 matrices contain 2x2 Pauli 2-choice matrices which are linked with spin $\frac{1}{2}$.

Identifying m_0 as the intrinsic force, arguing that one must find a linear equation in m_0 , and then linearizing ((2)) yields spin $\frac{1}{2}$. This, however, gives no information about Pauli's exclusion principle.

We argue that one must examine the intrinsic force in this case more closely. Rest mass m_0 implies that a particle has a center-of-mass. If there are two identical, but independent particles, there must be two center-of-mass points and the possibility of pushing one particle in one direction and the other, in another by a physical force. If this cannot be done, one cannot say one has two independent particles. As a result, one must consider the intrinsic force and possible physical reactions which it may undergo.

The first physical reaction is one involving momentum, i.e. impulse hits. If the two identical particles have center-of-mass points at different locations, one may clearly render two separate impulse hits and identify that there are indeed two particles. If, however, one imagines the two identical particles having the same center-of-mass point, one cannot render an impulse hit to one physically without interacting with the second one. In other words, one cannot push one in one direction and the other, in the other. We argue that there must be a second possible interaction mechanism which may separate the two particles in space and this may be done by having spin interact with a magnetic field. To separate the two particles, however, one cannot have both with spin up or down. One must have a combination of spin up and spin down.

Consider the case of both particles with spin up. Then there is no way to distinguish the particles. In such a case, one should write an antisymmetric wavefunction for space

$$W_1(x_1,p)W_2(x_2,p) - W_1(x_2,p)W_2(x_1,p) \quad ((3))$$

which may be multiplied by $|\text{spin up}\rangle_1 |\text{spin up}\rangle_2$ (or two spin downs) ((4))

For $x_1=x_2$, ((3)) is 0 showing that this is not allowed which is the statement of the Pauli exclusion principle. Given that both particles have spin up and the center-of-mass of each is at the same point, there does not exist a physical interaction (at the particle level) which can separate the two.

On the other hand, if one particle has spin up and the other spin down, even if the center-of-mass points are the same, a magnetic field can separate them into two different spatial regions as the original experiments which identified electron spin show. In such a case, one may have a symmetric spatial wavefunction

$$W_1(x_1,p)W_2(x_2,p) + W_1(x_2,p)W_2(x_1,p) \quad ((4))$$

and $x_1=x_2$ is fine because the spin wavefunction must be:

$$|\text{spin up}\rangle_1 |\text{spin down}\rangle_2 - |\text{spin down}\rangle_1 |\text{spin up}\rangle_2 \quad ((5))$$

As a result, we argue that the intrinsic force m_0 is critical in identifying the Pauli exclusion principle because it is the separation of the two identical particles (linked to the intrinsic force, i.e. the center of mass of each particle) which leads to the formulation of the Pauli principle for spin $\frac{1}{2}$ particles. In other words, it is really m_0 (rest mass) which leads to both the notion of spin $\frac{1}{2}$ and the Pauli exclusion principle for spin $\frac{1}{2}$ particles.

The Photon Case

The photon does not have a rest mass, so there is no center-of-mass which needs to be separated for two photons. The intrinsic force is the electric field. In the case of two particles with rest mass, if they have the same center-of-mass point one cannot use an impulse hit to

separate them and so must separate them via spin projections interacting with a magnetic field. For the photon, one does not need to separate the two. The electric fields add for identical photons. If they point in the same direction, then one has $2E$ (and $2B$) as well, but unlike the rest mass case in which E_1+E_2 for m_0, v and p_1+p_2 for m_0, v is the same as E for $2m_0, v$ and p for $2m_0, v$.

Such is not the case for a photon. A photon with $2E$ and $2B$ has an energy density of:

$$4 (.5\epsilon_0 E \cdot E + .5/\mu_0 B \cdot B) \quad ((6a)) \text{ while two photons with } E, B \text{ have}$$

$$2 (.5\epsilon_0 E \cdot E + .5/\mu_0 B \cdot B) \quad ((6b))$$

Even though the intrinsic force doubles ($2E$), the energy and momentum densities do not and one can see that one has two photons of E, B and not one of $2E, 2B$, something that was not possible with a rest mass. In the case of two identical rest masses at the same center-of-mass point, one must separate the two by force to show that there are two independent particles. This separation is exactly the idea of inertia which is why m_0 is chosen as the intrinsic force.

As a result, there are no restrictions for the spin 1 photon. We note that one may find the spin of a photon from considerations of its intrinsic force E which should appear in a linear equation, linked to p and E . One may show from Maxwell's equations that E and B go as $\cos(-\omega t + kx)$ and are perpendicular to each other and the direction of motion. One may then write:

$$d/dt \text{ partial } (.5\epsilon_0 E \cdot E + .5/\mu_0 B \cdot B) + 1/\mu_0 E \times B = 0 \quad ((7))$$

and linearize this to show that ϵ_{ijk} , the Levi-Civita symbol is the spin 1 matrix. Note: i represents the matrix label and i, j , the entries. One may also show that ω, k are linked to $E = \hbar \omega$ and $p = \hbar k$. One may note that in the spin $\frac{1}{2}$ case, the rotation range is 720 degrees, i.e

$$\exp(i \text{ spin } \theta) \quad ((8))$$

For a photon, spin 1 with circular polarization means that the E field is physically rotating with frequency E (proportional to p because $E=pc$) and energy density is related to $E \cdot E$ (and $B \cdot B$) and so one has physical classical angular momentum.

As a result, one may use symmetric wavefunctions for the photon (bosons) because there is no reason to have a factor become 0, like in the rest mass m_0 case.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the Pauli exclusion principle as well the notion of spin follow from the identification of an intrinsic force for a particle. Both a photon and electron have a momentum and energy associated with special relativity and a spatial free wavefunction of $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. Yet, they have very different spin and Pauli exclusion properties.

In (1), we argued that spin follows by finding an equation, linear in the intrinsic force, which is also linked to E, p and geometry. For a particle with rest mass m_0 , we argued that m_0 (inertia) is

the intrinsic force and that $-EE + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p} = -m_0 c^2$ (c=1) should be linearized, as Dirac did. This yields spin $\frac{1}{2}$. To see how the Pauli principle arises for this particle, one must consider the intrinsic force m_0 and note that two independent yet identical particles must have the possibility of interacting separately and obtain different center-of-mass points in an interaction. If one, however, places two identical particles such that they have the same center-of-mass, an impulse hit linked to \mathbf{p} (momentum) cannot move one one way and the other the other. One needs a different type of force to separate them and this may occur via opposite spin projections interacting with a magnetic field. If both particles have spin up, or both have spin down, the spatial wavefunction must be antisymmetric because one cannot have the two particles with the same center-of-mass point. Impulse hits to different center-of-mass points is required. If one wishes to have the center-of-mass points be the same, one may have a symmetric spatial wavefunction which does not vanish when $x_1=x_2$, but an antisymmetric spin wavefunction (spin up, spin down), such that making both spins up or down makes the wavefunction disappear. This is the Pauli principle for electrons, we argue. We note that for two m_0, v particles, $E+E$ and $\mathbf{p}+\mathbf{p}$ is the same as $E(2m_0, v)$ and $\mathbf{p}(2m_0, v)$. Thus, one cannot distinguish based on total energy or momentum.

For a photon, there is no rest mass and no center-of-mass considerations. The intrinsic force is E/c and if one has $2E/c$, one may ask: How does one know that one has two photons and not one with $2E/c$, $2\mathbf{p}$? In this case, the energy and momentum densities would differ and so given $2E/c$, one may interact with the energy density or momentum density and realize that there are two photons and not one. Thus, one does not have to worry about antisymmetric wavefunctions which disappear in certain conditions and one has the boson symmetric wavefunction result, we argue.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speculation on Quantum Spin, Intrinsic Force and Special Relativity Part 2 (zenodo, preprint, 2026)
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pauli_exclusion_principle